

An Observational Study on Xeroderma Pigmentosum: A Rare Genodermatosis in a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Introduction: Xeroderma Pigmentosum (XP) is a rare autosomal recessive genetic disorder characterized by defective DNA repair which leads to clinical and cellular hypersensitivity to ultraviolet radiation and other carcinogenic agents.

Aim: Xeroderma pigmentosum being a rare disorder, there is very less literature published on this from our region. Hence, we aim to study XP patients attending at our hospital.

Materials and Methods: Observational study was done on all the XP patients for duration of 6 months attending our hospital, proper history and examination was done.

Results: We observed 15 cases of XP, Of 15 patients, 5 were children of which 3 were from one family(figure 1) and 2 from another family(figure 2). Of the rest 10 adult patients, 6 were females and 4 were male patients of which 2 adult patients presented with squamous cell carcinoma. All patients had increased photo hypersensitivity and ocular involvement with some cutaneous manifestation. Neurological involvement was seen in 3 patients.

Conclusion: As various malignancies may occur at an early age, early diagnosis and management may prove fruitful. Advantage of genetic counseling implicating the effect of consanguineous marriages can prevent mortality and morbidity associated with this disorder and emphasis is to be done to same as it's an autosomal recessive disorder.

Keywords: Xeroderma pigmentosum, Autosomal recessive.

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Introduction

First described by Hebra and Kaposi in 1874, Xeroderma Pigmentosum (XP) is a rare autosomal recessive genetic disorder characterized by defective DNA repair which leads to clinical and cellular hypersensitivity to ultraviolet radiation and other carcinogenic agents [1]. Important clinical features are: intense cutaneous photosensitivity, xerosis, poikiloderma, actinic keratosis, acute burning under minimal sun exposure, hyperpigmented lentiginous macules, and malignant lesions in sun-exposed areas, including basocellular carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and melanoma. The epidemiology rates of this disorder are varied. Authors described different prevalence rates such as: 1:20,000 in Japan, 1:250,000 in the USA and approximately 2.3 per million in Western Europe [2]. Eight forms of the

disease are recognizable according to the features of the molecular defect and clinical aspects [3]. We present here siblings in two families presenting with xeroderma pigmentosum with varied neurological manifestations.

Here we present 15 patients of xeroderma pigmentosum duration of 6 months attending skin opd with various clinical presentation and complication.

Material and Methods

This is observational study on all the Xeroderma pigmentosum patients attending our hospital. Detail history including family history, demographic particulars, clinical features and complications

associated was recorded. No investigations were done for diagnosis or for treatment purpose.

Result

In this 6 months duration of observation study 5 were children and 10 were adult patients, of which 7 were male patients and 8 were female patients. Of this 5 were students, among which 3 left school because neurological or visual defects.

One male patient working in bank and other 9 are labourers and farmers. All the 15 patients had photohypersensitivity and one of the cutaneous manifestations.

Ten patients showed ocular involvement, in that 2 children vision was 6/36. Of 5 patients showing neurological involvement, two patients were diagnosed with xeroderma pigmentosum with Squamous cell carcinoma (table 1).

Table 1: Clinical symptoms

Sl No	Clinical symptoms	No of Patients involved
1	Photohypersensitivity	15
2	Ocular involvement	10
3	Neurological involvement	05
4	Cutaneous presentation like (xerosis, poikiloderma, actinic keratosis)	15
5	Malignances like (Squamous cell carcinoma, Basal cell carcinoma and Melanoma)	02

Figure 1: One family three childrens with XP

Figure 2: Another child with XP of different family

Discussion

Xeroderma pigmentosum is autosomal recessive (AR) genetic disease caused by defects in the normal repair of DNA of various cutaneous and ocular cell types damaged by exposure to sunlight. The basic defect underlying the clinical manifestations is a nucleotide excision repair (NER) defect leading to a defective repair of DNA damaged by ultra violet radiation [4]. This disease is characterized by photosensitivity, hyperpigmentation and ichthyosis in sun exposed areas, a 1000-fold increase in the risk of basal and squamous cell carcinomas and melanomas of the skin and eyes [5]. Increased mutagenesis is accepted as the basis of elevated skin cancer incidence in XP6. Roughly 30% of XP patients develop progressive neurologic symptoms.

There are seven complementation groups of XP (XP-A to -G) caused by defective NER, corresponding to mutations in the genes encoding XPA, XPB, XPC, XPD, XPE, XPF and XPG. It is more commonly seen in populations where marriage of close blood relatives is common [5].

Xeroderma Pigmentosum has been reported worldwide in all races with an overall prevalence of 1-4% per million. The diagnosis of XP is considered when a young patient presents with marked photosensitivity, xerosis and multiple pigmented lesions. Phototesting may be performed showing reduced minimal erythema dose in the 290 to 340 nm range [7].

Although photo-testing is widely available in the developed world it is neither sensitive nor specific for XP. Treatment of the disorder includes avoidance of Ultra violet radiation, topical application of 5- fluorouracil to treat actinic keratoses, and regular evaluation by an ophthalmologist, dermatologist, and neurologist.

Genetic counseling is an important aspect as an increased incidence of consanguineous marriages has been reported with this disorder [5].

Conclusion

Xeroderma pigmentosum is a life threatening disorder, as various malignancies may occur at an early age, so early diagnosis and management may prove fruitful. Genetic counseling implicating the effect on consanguineous marriages should be emphasized as it can be prevented with prior counseling, considering the morbidity with which a XP patient should live and associated mortality.

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